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ETHNOGRAPHY AND TOPONOMY OF THE VILLAGES OF ISHTIKHAN DISTRICT.

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Annotation

This article studies the ethnic origin of the population of the villages located in the Ishtikhan district and the toponymy of the villages based on the field survey conducted in the district and the collected data. The data collected during this study and all the scientific work done to date on the ethnic history of the population of the Ishtikhan district were studied and a scientific conclusion was given.

Key words: Miyanqol, Qanjig'ali, Mitan, Xitoy, Barlos, Shixlar, Qipchoq, "Shajarayi turk", Turkman, Bahrin, Oyinli, Mirzoqul, Urug', Nurota, Arab, Kesovli, Tervuz-tovoq, Orlot, Saroy, Etnotoponim, Chaxar, Qo'rlı, Boyto'pi, Qatog'on.

In the study of the history of Uzbekistan, the study of the history and ethnography of districts and villages remains relevant. In particular, the history and ethnography of Ishtikhan district has not been sufficiently studied to date. We can find a lot of information about the history of the district in various sources and literature. However, in-depth research has not been carried out on the ethnic origin, ethnic composition and toponymy of the district population.

Ishtikhan district is located in the Samarkand region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The district is located in the northern part of the city of Samarkand and is distinguished by its rich historical and cultural heritage. Ishtikhan district is one of the important districts of the Samarkand region, bordering the Kattakurgan, Qoshrobot, Payariq and Pasdargam districts of the region. The district is located in the ancient Miyanqol oasis, between two branches of the Zarafshan River - Akdarya and Karadarya. The northern borders of Ishtikhan district consist of mountains and hills, connecting with the plains on the southern slopes of the Nurota mountain range. The territory of the district consists of mountains, valleys and fields. The climate here is mainly dry and hot, with high temperatures in summer. These areas have long attracted the attention of people, who have been engaged in animal husbandry and agriculture in these areas. The ethnic composition of the population of the villages of Ishtikhan district is mainly Uzbeks, in addition, the district is also home to Russians, Tajiks, Koreans, Ukrainians, Tatars, Armenians and other ethnic minorities. The district is inhabited by people belonging to various Uzbek tribes and clans. Representatives of more than 20 ethnic groups are registered in the center and villages of the Ishtikhan district. They are: Turkmen, Chinese, Mitan, Barlos, Beklar, Alpine, Ayjoryk, Tuvodok, Karakalpak, Iranian, Arab, Georgian, Eshon, Toqchi, Naiman, Jovi, Kanjigali, Topchi, Tashim, Khasangori, Nurim, Alakai, Bolgali, Beshbola, Itborboy, Boytopi, Aytamgali tribes.¹ In addition, representatives of the Kungirov, Mongolian, Kipchak and Kazakh tribes and clans also live there. The names of many villages are associated with the names of tribes and clans. Some of these include the following villages: Barlos village, Kesovli village, Minglar village, Zhuvantayok village, Kanjikali village, Kaychili village. The name of a certain tribe and clan

¹ N.Elmuurodov, "Zarafshon vohasi o'zbek xalqi etnik guruhları". Educational and methodological guide, Samarkand-SamSIFL, 2008, page 41

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plays an important role in the naming of these villages. However, most of these villages are not inhabited by people belonging to the clan indicated by the name of the village. Historically, these villages were inhabited by other tribal clans, and later representatives of other tribes and clans may have come and settled these lands. According to the results of field research and field surveys conducted in the Ishtikhan district, the villages of the district are inhabited by the following ethnotoponyms and clans.

Chovli village is a village name located in the Ishtikhan district. The meaning is interpreted as “spoon”. There are also forms of the name Chovli: jov, jov, jovi. Chovli is the name of a small clan belonging to the Kirqoyak clan of the Kipchaks, and people belonging to the clan of the same name live in this village. The tamga (stamp) of the people living in the village of Chovli was in the shape of a spoon. People belonging to the jovi clan live in the village of Opka, Ishtikhan district.

Kesovli village is a village associated with the name of another clan in the district. Kesovli village is inhabited by representatives of the clan called Kesovli, which is part of the Kungirat tribe. The reason for this name of the clan was their tamga in the form of a kesov. Therefore, this clan was called Kesovli. “Kesov” was considered a household item that dug a hearth.

Aqcho'rag'asi village is the name of a village located in the Ishtikhan district. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the Aqcho'ragasi clan, a branch of the Qatagon tribe.

Arabkhona village - there is a village of the same name in the Ishtikhan district, as in other regions and districts. This village is inhabited by people of Arab ethnic origin. The settlement of people in this village in Central Asia dates back to the period of the Arab invasion, that is, to the VIII-IX centuries AD, and those who settled there came later. Currently, the residents of this village claim to be from the Arab clan of Uzbeks. The residents of the Arabkhona village are of Arab ethnic origin, but today they are considered a clan that is part of the Uzbek clans. Ethnic Arabs also live in the villages of Ulqishlok, Tarvuz-tavok, Koktepa, and Rovot.

Kuljomon village is the name of another village in the Ishtikhan district. The name of this village is associated with the name of the Kuljomon clan, a small branch of the Jigaltoy clan, which is a branch of the Akqipchak clan, which is part of the Kipchak tribe. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the Kuljomon clan.

Khalajon village is the name of a village located in the district. This name is considered an ethnotonym and is associated with the name of the Khalaj tribe, one of the ancient Turkic tribes. Representatives of the Khalaj tribe have been integrated into the population here.

Beshbola village is the name of another village located in the district. Beshbola is actually an ethnonym, the name of a clan in the Oynli (Oyinni) division of the Kungiroi tribe. The population of the clan of this name lives in the Beshbola village.

Qiyot village is an ethnotonym found in the Ishtikhan district. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the same clan. Qiyot is the name of 92 Uzbek clans, and its meaning is described as “a flood flowing from the mountain”.

Qanjigali village is the name of another village located in the district. Qanjigali is a large branch of the Qogiroi tribe. This branch is sometimes referred to as “Qanjiga”. People belonging to the Qanjigali clan live in this village. Nine small branches of the Qanjigali clan are located in the Zarband village of Ishtikhan district.

Arlot (Orlot) – one of the villages of Ishtikhan district, inhabited by the Orlot tribe. The village of Arlot is pronounced Orlot by the local population. The origin of the word Arlot comes from the name

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of one of the four Mongol tribes formed for Genghis Khan's son Chigatoy. The Arlot clan is also recorded among 92 Uzbek clans.

Kangni village – the name of one of the villages located in the district. It is possible that the toponym Kangni is a modified form of the toponym Kangar, that is, Kangli, and this ethnonym is very similar to the name of the ancient Turkic tribe Kangli.²

Zhuvantayok village – one of the villages located in the Ishtikhan district, associated with the name of the clan. The Juvantayok Turkic tribes are one of the monotheistic tribes, and this clan is found among the Uzbeks and Kazakhs. This clan is also called Argin. The village of Juvantayok is named after this clan. Because people belonging to this clan live in this village.

Kyrgyz village is one of the villages in the district named after the clan. The Kyrgyz clan is a clan that is part of the 92-bov Uzbek clans. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the Kyrgyz clan.

Yukori Qing'ir village is the toponym of a village located in the Ishtikhan district. Qing'ir is the name of one of the Turkic tribes, which is described by the people with the Turkic word "Kong'ir". This tribe is also associated with the Bijanak tribe.

Yukori Saroy village is the name of another village located in the district. The Saray tribe is a tribe that is part of the 92-bovli Uzbek tribes. Representatives of the Saray tribe live in this village. As for the meaning of the village, it is interpreted as "the upper village where the Saray people live".

To'por village is one of the villages located in the Ishtikhan district. To'por is the name of a small tribe that is part of the Kungirat tribe. People belonging to the tribe of the same name live in the village.

O'tarchi village is the name of a village located in the district. O'tarchi is the name of one of the Uzbek tribes. The original meaning of the word "Otarchi" is interpreted as "temporary resident" or "passerby". This village is inhabited by representatives of the Otarchi clan.

Sari Shirin village is a village in the Ishtikhan district. This is an ethnotoponym. It is related to the Shirin clan, one of the Turkic tribes, and representatives of the Shirin and Chinese clans live in this village. This village is also called Shirin. Shikhlar village is the name of a village located in the Ishtikhan district. This village is inhabited by people who call themselves "shikhlar", that is, "sheikhs". The word "shikh" is considered a modified form of the word "sheikh" and means "leader", "elder". The Shikh clan is also recorded among Uzbek tribes. The reason why people living in this village are called by this name is because religious and intellectual scholars who grew up in this village have grown up. The population of the village is considered to be the descendants of these people. Shikhlar village is also inhabited by people who are of Tatar origin, eshans, toqchis, and people who are currently assimilated into the Uzbek community.³

Chaqaq village is the name of a village located in the vicinity of the city of Miytan, Ishtikhan district. The meaning of the word Chaqaq is interpreted as "urban". The Chaqaq clan may be a corrupted form of the Mongolian word "chakhar" or "sakhar". The meaning of both words is interpreted as "city". It is clear from this that in ancient times people who were related to the clan of the same name lived in the village of Chaqaq. Today, representatives of the Moytan (Miytan) clan

² O'zbekiston joy nomlarining izohli lug'ati [Matn]: dictionary / creators R.Y.Xudoyberganov [and others.]. – Tashkent: Donishmand ziyosi, 2022. Page 572.

³ Field survey 2024.05.27 Ishtikhan district.

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live in this village. Representatives of the Moytan (Miytan) clan also live in the villages of Chaqar, Qorli, and Qayirma. Two small divisions of the Moytan (Miytan) clan, the Boylar and the Parkar, live in the village of Qayirma.

Asadbahrin village is the name of one of the streams in the Ishtikhan district. According to historians, the word Bahrin is the name of one of the Turkicized Mongol tribes. In the 17th-19th centuries, people belonging to the Bahrin tribe settled in the territories of the Zarafshan oasis. The meaning of the word Bahrin is ancient Turkic and means “a large bird of prey, that is, a type of falcon.” As for the naming of the Asadbahrin stream, which flows through the Ishtikhan district, in ancient times people belonging to the Bahrin tribe lived around this stream. Later, this stream began to be called by this ethnotoponym. Currently, representatives of the Kipchak tribe live in this village.

Boyto'bi (Boyto'pi) – another ethnonym that is part of the district. Boyto'pi is the name of one of the Turkic tribes. Boyto'pi village is pronounced Boyto'pi by the local population. The reason for the village's name was the people belonging to the Boyto'pi clan living in this village.

Barlos village – another village name located in the vicinity of the city of Miytan in Ishtikhan district. Barlos is the name of one of the Turkic tribes, and its meaning is interpreted as “brave, brave, commander”. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the Barlos clan.⁴ In addition, people belonging to these clans also live in the villages of Qorli, Yo'gantepa, Hazarbobo, Zarband of Ishtikhan district.

Minglar village – this village is one of the villages inhabited by the Ming in Ishtikhan district. Ming 92 is considered one of the most prominent clans among the Uzbek clans. In addition to the Uzbek people, the Ming tribe is also found in the composition of such peoples as the Nugay, Kyrgyz, Bashkir, Karkalpak, Kazakh, Turkmen, Altai, Tuva, and Mongolian Khakass. Representatives of the Ming and Iranian tribes live in the Minglar village.⁵

Kelachi village is the name of another village in the district. The name of this village is associated with the Kelachi clan, a small branch of the Uzbek clan. This village is inhabited by representatives of the population of the same name.

Qatogon village is a village in the Ishtikhan district, which is associated with another ethnotoponym. Qatogon is a large clan that is part of the Uzbek clans. People belonging to the clan of the same name live in the village of Qatogon.

Tumor village is the name of a village located in the Ishtikhan district. Tumor is a small subdivision of the Kipchak tribe. Representatives of the Dumar clan live in this village.

Qatogonsaroy village is the name of a village located in the district. Representatives of the Saray clan live in this village. The Saray clan holds a special place among the 92 Uzbek clans.

Tentakovul or Tentak village is a village named after another clan in the district. The name of these villages is associated with the name of the Tentak clan living in this village. The Tentak is a small subdivision of the Kungirov tribe. The meaning of the word Tentakovul is interpreted as “a village where tentaks live”.

Badoy (Bodoy) village is the name of one of the villages in Ishtikhan district. The Baday is the name of a clan that is part of the nomadic Uzbek tribe. There are also villages named Badayovul and Qoriqbaday in Ishtikhan district, and people belonging to the Baday clan live in these villages.

⁴ Field survey 2024.05.27 Ishtikhan district.

⁵ Nurali Norboyev. “O'zbek elining qabila va urug'lari haqida”, Tashkent, 1997, page 31.

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Therefore, the term Baday is used in the toponyms of these villages. That is, it means “a village where the Badays live”.

Toqmon village is the name of another village in the district. Toqmon is a small branch of the Kungirost clan. The name of this village is associated with the name of the Toqmon clan living in this village.

Qoshtamgali village is one of the villages located in the territory of Ishtikhan district. The village is divided into two parts: Yukory Qoshtamgali and Tov Qoshtamgali. Qoshtamgali is the name of one of the Uzbek clans, which is part of the Kungirost, Yuz, Naayman and Nurota Turkmen. The reason for this name of the clan is the shape of the tamga in the form of a “double” or “double”. The inhabitants of these villages belong to the Qoshtamgali clan, which is part of the Nurota Turkmen.

Qoriqbaday village is another ethnotoponym located in the district. The name of this village is apparently connected with the name of the hay reaper of the Badai clan. People belonging to the Badai clan live in this village.

Qongirost village is the name of a village located in the Ishtikhan district. The name of a large tribe belonging to the Kungirost 92 clan Uzbek clans. The existence of cities, canals, and places named after the Kungirost clan proves that the Kungirosts have been in Central Asia since ancient times.⁶ The village of Kungirost is inhabited by representatives of the Kungirost and Bek clans.

Damchogatoy village is the name of another village in the district. We can give the following explanation for the toponym of this village. The word “dam” in the toponym of the village is used in relation to a place where water does not flow, that is, where water accumulates in one place. The word Chogatoy is the name of one of the Turkic tribes. It is clear from this that it means a place where the Chagatoy clan, which lives in a place where water accumulates, lives.

Barokkhislok village is the name of one of the villages located in the district. The name of this village is associated with the name of the Turkic “barok” tribe. Barok is mainly part of the Qatagon, Kungirost and Nurota Turkmen Kazakh clans. If we think about which tribe the population living in this village belongs to, it is closer to the truth that the villagers are part of the Nurota Turkmen.

Mirzakul village is the name of a village in Ishtikhan district. The population of the village belongs to the Chinese-Kipchak tribe. In addition, in villages such as Avliyotepa, Do’stlik, Khojaly, Yo’gontepa, Chinok, Ravot, Shilkim, Oktepa, Taka, Yugontepa, Saray and Shirin, the population of the Chinese (Chinese-Kipchak) tribe also lives. The Chinese-Kipchak tribe is found in the Karakalpaks and Uzbeks, as well as in the Kyrgyz.

Kaychili village is the name of a village associated with the name of a tribe in the district. This village is inhabited by people belonging to the “Kaychili” tribe, a division of the Kungirost tribe. The village is named after the tribe here. The tamga of the tribes living in this village was in the form of scissors.

Karakhan village is the name of another village located in the district. This village is inhabited by representatives of the Jigaltoy clan, which is part of the Akqipchaks, which are part of the Kipchaks. The Karakhan clan is a small clan within the Jigaltoy clan.

Shegerbey village is another ethnotoponym in the Ishtikhan district. This village is also inhabited by representatives of the Shegerbey clan, which is a branch of the Jigaltoy clan, which is part of the Kipchaks.

⁶ Nurali Norboyev. “O’zbek elining qabila va urug’lari haqida”, Tashkent, 1997, page 12.

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Karakhoni village is a village located in the district. The inhabitants of this village consider themselves descendants of Saint Karakhoni. Therefore, the representatives of the Karakhoni khoja clan live in this village. Therefore, the village is called by the ethnotoponym Karakhoni.

Karakoyli village is another village within the district. The name of the village is associated with the name of the Karakoyli clan, which is part of the Uzbek clans. The Karakoyli clan is considered a subdivision of the Kirg clan. This clan is also found in the Bin, Yuz and Turkmen. The residents of the Karakoyli village are part of this clan.

Karacha village is the name of a village associated with the name of the clan, which is part of the Ishtikhan district. People belonging to the Karacha clan live in the village.⁷ The Karacha clan is a subdivision of the Kirg, Qatogan and Lakay (Lakay) tribes.

Chimqorgan village is the name of a village located in the Chimqorgan mahalla of the Ishtikhan district. The village got its name from the hills and mountains located in the village area, and the village is located among high hills resembling a mound. The village is inhabited by representatives of the Alpli, Oyjorik and Tovodok clans, which are small clan subdivisions.⁸

Zarband village - located in the district, Zarband village is home to the Khoja, Topchi, Tashim, Kanjigali and Barlos clans. The population of the Kanjigali clan belongs to 9 subdivisions. They are: Tashim, Khasangori, Nurim, Alakai, Balgali, Beshbola, Itborboy, Boytopi and Aytamgali.⁹ People belonging to the Nurim subdivision of the Kanjigali clan also live in the villages of Sebiston and Pitov.

We can meet many more representatives of different clans in the villages of Ishtikhan district. For example: in the village of Opka, we can find the Jovi, Naiman, Eshon, Toqchi clans, in the village of Koktepa the Arab, Naiman clans, in the village of Pitov the Kanjigali, Beklar clans, in the village of Qorli the Barlos, Moytan clans, in the village of Kamar the Chimma, in the village of Toytovuq the Kenagas, in the village of Rovot the Georgian, Arabs, in the village of Shovan the Turkmen, in the village of Khojali the Turkmen, in the village of Yukoritepa the Chinese, Barlos, in the villages of Khozorbobo, Khna, Bahrin the Kipchak clans, in the villages of Khoja Isokjon, Burkhankhodja, Saray, Kattakangli, Shaykhislam, Safokhaja the Eshon, in the village of Uzbekkurgan the Mytan clans. This situation is also true in many other villages. The origin and location of the clans depends on the ethnic groups in the Zarafshan oasis.

In conclusion, we can say that the tribes and clans living in the Ishtikhan district are very similar to the ethnic groups living in the neighboring district located in the Zarafshan oasis. These similarities are the same as the ethnic clans in the territories of Qoshrabot, Kattakurgan, Payariq, Jomboy and Nurota district of Navoi region. There are also clans in the Ishtikhan district that differ from other districts. During the study, it was observed that clans live in mixed conditions in some of the villages in the district. These villages were formed after the settlement of clans and representatives of different clans from other villages migrated to these villages. The clans living in the district have preserved their history and culture to this day.

⁷ Field survey 2024.10.12, Ishtikhan district.

⁸ N.Elmuurodov, "Zarafshon vohasi o'zbek xalqi etnik guruhlari". Educational and methodological guide, Samarkand-SamSIFL, 2008, page 61-63.

⁹ N.Elmuurodov, "Zarafshon vohasi o'zbek xalqi etnik guruhlari". Educational and methodological guide, Samarkand-SamSIFL, 2008, page 102.

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